

Teacher-Related Factors as Predictors of Classroom Behaviours: Implications for Teaching Reading Skills to the Students with Learning Disabilities

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ABSTRACT

Teacher classroom behaviour has been documented as a main determinant of the classroom learning activities, interactions, and student outcomes. The study investigated the predicting influence of three teacher-related factors (teacher self-efficacy, year of teaching experience, and level of teachers' school which could be primary level or secondary level) on teachers' classroom behaviours. The descriptive research design of the correlational type was adopted. The sample size was 132 (female=76, male=56) primary and secondary school teachers in Ibadan Metropolis, Oyo State, Nigeria. The respondents had the average age of 20-59 years ($\bar{x} = 39.5$ years). Two validated and relevant instruments namely, teacher self-efficacy and teacher classroom behaviours scales were used in this study. Data was analyzed using descriptive statistics, Pearson product moment correlation and multiple regression analysis. The result revealed that is a positive relationship between teacher self-efficacy, years of teaching experience and teacher classroom behaviour. The independent variables jointly contributed 16.9% of the variance to the prediction of teacher classroom behaviour when taken together. Teacher self-efficacy was most potent on predicting teacher classroom behaviour. The study has implications for teachers, especially those who teach reading skills to students with learning disabilities. The study recommends that teachers should develop high teaching self-efficacy that is capable of enabling them to perform their duties effectively.

Keywords: *Teacher Classroom Behaviour, Teacher Self-Efficacy, Year of Teaching Experience, Reading Skills, The Primary or Secondary School Setting*

Introduction

Teachers play significant roles in their various classrooms. They initiate and drive overall school improvement (Rechsteiner et al., 2022), serve as the principal contributors to classroom interactions (Egeberg et al., 2021) and are responsible for curriculum implementation (Alsubaie, 2016). Teachers' central goal in the school system is to provide quality education to all students (Lazarus, 2019) through making meaningful impact on their academic achievement, attitudes and behaviours (Blazar, 2016). Teachers determine what goes on in the classrooms. They set the tone

of their classrooms, model the way for their students, stay alert to the behavioural challenges that ensue in the classroom in order to proffer solutions. Also, teachers create classroom environments that are conducive for students (Fraser & Walberg, 2005).

In the teaching learning process, classroom behaviours demonstrated by teachers have been related to teachers' professional practices. Teacher classroom behaviour is an umbrella term and a multidimensional construct that comprise various components. This study tends to emphasize three aspects of classroom behaviours of teachers as follows: behaviour management, use of instructional strategies and use of motivational strategies. Behaviour management refers to the efforts made by teachers before a misbehaviour occurs, in order to avert student misbehaviour and the response given to the misbehaviour when it happens. Behaviour management, points to the establishment of teacher expectations, monitoring and teacher behaviour and the provision of opportunities for student input (Egeberg et al., 2021).

Teachers make use of instructional strategies, techniques, methods and interventions in their classrooms to achieve their set objectives and for efficient lesson delivery. The appropriate choice of instructional strategies leads to improved student outcomes. Effective teachers are those who set learning objectives and adopt the right methodologies in the teaching learning process (Egeberg et al. 2021). They prepare, design and structure routines that take place in their classrooms, utilize numerous teaching approaches and strategies so as to bring about students' active participation and engagement.

Evidence has shown that instructional strategies that have led to enhanced learning outcomes among students with special educational needs like those with learning disabilities, include instructional groupings and peer-mediated reading practices (Wanzek et al., 2010; Haager & Vaughn, 2013; Boardman et al., 2016); collaborative strategic reading (Lazarus, 2009, Boardman et al., 2016), phonics instruction (Haager & Vaughn, 2013), story grammar instruction (Alves et al., 2015) and transactional strategy instruction (Lazarus & Ige, 2017). Bonney et al. (2015) added that the lecture method, small group instruction and hands-on learning tasks are essential instructional strategies. Khalaf and Santi (2016) highlighted classroom-based reading activities for students with learning disabilities that include repeated reading, partner reading, rhyming, syllable, phoneme awareness activities, daily explicit vocabulary instruction and the use of context clue tasks.

The use of several motivational strategies that have a strong positive influence in motivating students to learn (Guilloteaux & Dörnyei, 2008; Dörnyei & Kubanyiova, 2014; Henry et al., 2018) can lead to improved student outcomes. Teachers sometimes, create opportunities for class conversations, admit that making errors is part of the learning process, provide and sustain an inspiring classroom environment (Kirondo, 2014). In addition, Kirondo (2014) found that lack of adequate subject mastery by teachers, a large class size and inability to use instructional aids and materials affect teacher use of motivational strategies negatively. This finding buttresses the need for teacher competency in his/her subject area as well as the importance of teacher use of relevant teaching aids and materials in the classroom.

Besides, the efficacy of the implementation of motivational strategies in the classroom by teachers has been confirmed. Studies have shown that the process of providing simple

motivational conditions, creating initial motivation, sustaining and defending motivation has been found to be one of the best plans to bring about efficient learning (Kirondo, 2014). Some motivational strategies focus on intellectual behaviours such as monitoring and strategy use, while others are non-cognitive aspects such as perception, beliefs and attitudes, or both. Irrespective of the type of motivational strategy that the teacher adopts, it is instrumental to enhanced academic achievement of learners.

Literature review

Reading instruction and students with learning disabilities

Reading, a critical skill in the educational success of all students can be broadly categorized into word recognition and reading comprehension sub-skills. While word recognition entails the ability of a reader to recognize words rapidly and automatically, reading comprehension involves making meaning from printed material, by coordinating a number of complex processes that involve language, word reading, word knowledge, and fluency (Cain et al., 2004; Paris, 2005). Without adequate reading skills, students can struggle in many subject areas (Lazarus, 2019). However, the majority of students with learning disabilities experience reading difficulties which hinders their progress in academics and life (Lazarus, 2009). Several studies have revealed that English learners with learning disabilities benefit from instructional materials that underscore important reading skills such as phonological awareness, fluency, vocabulary development, and reading comprehension (Lazarus, 2009; Khalaf & Santi, 2016). It is hoped that a good understanding of teacher-related factors (teacher self-efficacy, years of teaching experience and level of teachers' school) that could predict teacher classroom behaviours and in so doing influence the teaching of reading skills to students with learning disabilities would be of great importance to educators.

Teacher self-efficacy and their classroom behaviours

Dicke et al. (2014) asserted that teacher self-efficacy defines their ability to plan and carry out actions that enable them to utilize behaviour management strategies, instructional and motivational strategies that can create a positive learning environment. Dicke et al. (2014) found that classroom disturbances, misconduct and emotional instability among students are the results of the lower levels of self-efficacy among teachers. This implies that when teachers have high self-efficacy, they will be able to manage their classrooms well. Tschannen-Moran et al. (2007) posited that there is the possibility that high self-efficacy among teachers led to effective management of behaviour in the classroom. Another study demonstrated that the higher the self-efficacy of teachers the higher the quality of classroom instruction (Holzberger et al., 2013).

Teachers with a high sense of self-efficacy are more engaged in providing differentiated instruction to their students (Suprayogi et al. (2017). Other studies (Chao et al., 2017; Miller et al., 2017) have found that high teacher self-efficacy leads to having students who are focused on the tasks they are involved in doing. Furthermore, teacher self-efficacy is built through competence and confidence. So, any teacher who lacks both skills will have a weak self-efficacy. Teachers with a higher self-efficacy can control the classroom and provide quality instructions

by using different instructional strategies that can enhance students' participation and learning (Holzberger et al., 2013).

The study of Mitchell (2019) revealed that self-efficacious teachers adopted classroom management (reward, preventive, initial corrective, and later corrective) strategies unlike their counterparts with low self-efficacy. This is because teacher self-efficacy is fundamental to a better classroom environment that is free from aggression and all manners of inappropriate behaviours. Therefore, the reduction in the gap between teacher self-efficacy and classroom management would lead to an increase in the academic achievements of students and a positive adjustment in student behaviours (Mitchell, 2019).

Years of teaching experience, and teacher classroom behaviours

Saeedi (2016) found that with respect to classroom management, there were significant differences between experienced and inexperienced English as Foreign Language (EFL) teachers. While experienced EFL teachers exerted more classroom control over their students, their counterparts, that is inexperienced EFL teachers showed less control over their students. The finding of Unal and Unal (2012) showed that experienced teachers managed their classrooms better than inexperienced teachers. Amadi and Allagoa (2017) found remarkable correlations between teacher-related variables like years of teaching experience, educational qualification and age and the effectiveness of teachers' classroom management styles. Nikolaros (2014) found that teachers with long teaching experience (11-30 years) were favourably disposed to the use of direct instructional strategies in teaching students with emotional disturbances than those with short teaching experience.

Shoulders and Krei (2015) discussed the influence of years of experience with respect to teacher self-efficacy. In a Follow-up post hoc analysis carried out by these researchers, there was a significant difference between 0-4 years of teaching experience and 15 or more years of experience in both teacher efficacy in instructional practices and classroom management. Podolsky et al. (2019) revealed that there is a positive relationship between teaching experience and student achievement. These researchers also added that the more experienced a teacher is the better for the school and colleagues. The experienced teachers are those the researchers described as effective teachers.

The veracity of an assertion by the Directions Evidence and Policy Research Group (DEPRG), Ontario (2014) that "all things being equal, teachers with more experience are better teachers" has been queried. Irvine (2019) examined the claim that teaching experience has a relationship with teacher effectiveness, as measured by student achievement gains. Finding revealed that long years of teaching experience do not necessarily translate to effectiveness among teachers. Therefore, suggesting that a direct and linear relationship between teacher experience and effectiveness appears to be a simplistic viewpoint.

Level of teachers school (primary or secondary) and teacher classroom behaviours

It was found that teachers in the primary school level who teach younger students possessed higher self-efficacy than their counterparts in other levels of school setting (Wolters &

Daugherty, 2007). This finding supports the fact that the age of students was closely associated with teacher self-efficacy in classroom management and student engagement. The finding of Klassen and Chiu (2010) equally revealed that high teacher self-efficacy was common among those teachers who taught largely young learners in the primary schools. This finding is also in congruence with those of Wolters and Daugherty (2007).

Teachers in primary schools demonstrated more willingness and preparedness in the management of students who exhibited behavioural deficits. However, there were no significant correlations between self-efficacy of teachers and the level of school where they teach, that is, either primary or secondary settings (Baker, 2005). A study by Lee et al. (2012) found that primary and secondary school teachers differed in their teaching self-efficacy and in pedagogical conceptual change in favour of primary school teachers. Teachers at the primary school had higher teacher self-efficacy than secondary school teachers. The findings of the study also showed that primary and secondary school teachers were potent moderators between years in teaching and self-efficacy.

From the foregoing, it appears that previous studies largely focused on teacher self-efficacy, classroom management, teacher demographics and their relationships with student outcomes. However, there was little consideration for the influence of teacher-related factors (teacher self-efficacy, year of teaching experience and level of teachers' school) on the classroom behaviours of teachers in the study area. This study, therefore, was carried out to investigate teacher-related factors (teacher self-efficacy, years of teaching experience and level of teachers' school which could be primary level or secondary level) that can influence teachers' classroom behaviours (behaviour management, instructional strategies and motivational strategies usage).

Research questions

The following questions were answered in the study.

1. What is the pattern of the relationship between teacher-related factors (teacher self-efficacy, years of teaching experience, and level of teachers' school) and classroom behaviours among teachers in Ibadan Metropolis?
2. To what extent do teacher-related factors (teacher self-efficacy, years of teaching experience, and level of teachers' school) jointly contribute to the prediction of classroom behaviours among teachers in Ibadan Metropolis?
3. What is the relative contribution of each of the independent variables (teacher self-efficacy, years of teaching experience, and level of teachers' school) to the prediction of the criterion variable (classroom behaviours) among teachers in Ibadan Metropolis?

Methodology

Design

The present study, adopted the descriptive research design of the correlational type to incorporate the different components of the study in a clear and logical way. The correlational design was considered to be the most suitable for the study since it involved collection of data on existing phenomenon and determining whether or not there exist a relationship among the four

quantifiable variables namely, teacher-related factors (teacher self-efficacy, year of teaching experience and level of teachers' school) and teacher classroom behaviour) the researcher is interested in without any form of manipulation.

Setting

Ibadan is the capital of Oyo State and it is situated in Southwestern Nigeria. It remains the largest traditional Yoruba city and is located on a major transport route to the northern parts of Nigeria. For the purpose of administration, there are 11 Local Government Areas (LGAs) in Ibadan. While the Ibadan semi-urban LGAs are six in number, Ibadan urban LGAs are five. The premier university in Nigeria, the University of Ibadan is located in this city. There are also a lot of higher educational institutions in the city. Several public and private primary and secondary schools are located in Ibadan and its suburbs. The researcher deemed it fit to situate the present study in the city of Ibadan because it is easily accessible to the researcher who works in the University of Ibadan, Ibadan. Also, the city has a large population of which school-aged students are many in number. It is considered appropriate to seek ways to improve the academic stance of the teeming population of youngsters in Ibadan through this study.

Sample and sampling technique

The sample size was one hundred and thirty-two (132) primary and secondary school teachers in Ibadan Metropolis, Nigeria. There were 76 (57.6%) females and 56 (42.4%) males in the average age of 20-59 years ($\bar{x} = 39.5$). The simple random sampling of the ballot method was used to select five Local Government Areas (LGAs) out of eleven LGAs in Ibadan Metropolis, Oyo State, Nigeria. The LGAs selected were Ibadan North, South West, South-East, Egbeda and Oluyole. Thereafter, thirteen public schools comprising four primary and nine secondary schools were also selected using the same ballot method from the five participating LGAs. There were 106 secondary school teachers of which 53 (40.2%) of them teach in junior secondary and 53 (40.2%) teach in senior secondary schools, while primary school teachers were only 26 (19.7%). The years of teaching experience of respondents range from less than 1 year to 24 years and above.

Measures

The Teacher Self-Efficacy and Teacher Classroom Behaviours scales were used in this study.

(i) The Teacher Efficacy Scale: This scale has two sections which are, Section A and B. Section A elicited respondents' demographic information such as gender, age, educational qualification, educational role, years of teaching experience and level of teacher's school. Section B is the adopted 12 item Teacher Efficacy Scale, by Nie et al. (2012). This scale is a revised version of Teacher Sense of Efficacy Scale (TSES) by Tschannem-Moran and Hoy (2001). It consists of three factors: efficacy for instruction, efficacy for classroom management and efficacy for motivation. 12 items of the revised version of the TSES are measured on a five-point Likert scale from 1, "not well at all", to 5, "very well". To revise the TSES, Nie et al. (2012) tested twenty-one items in the original TSES which they rephrased to suit the objectives

of their review. The researchers removed three questions from the long 24-item version of TSES because they reported that these questions did not directly represent motivational strategies. The researcher trial-tested the Teacher Efficacy Scale and obtained a Cronbach's alpha of 0.88. This is considered appropriate.

(ii) Teacher Classroom Behaviour Scale: Three components of teacher classroom behaviours were measured in this scale. These are teacher use of: behaviour management strategies, instructional strategies and motivational strategies. a. Behaviour Management Strategies Scale (BMSS): This scale is an adapted version of the Mathematics Enhancement Classroom Observation Record Scale (MECORS) designed by Schaffer et al. (1998). The scale assesses how frequently teachers use behaviour management in their classrooms. The revised scale included seven items that were scored on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (never) to 5 (always). The BMSS has a Cronbach's alpha of 0.88 showing its internal consistency reliability. b. Instructional Strategies Scale (ISS): This scale was adapted from the MECORS and it was used to assess teachers' use of effective instructional strategies in the classroom. The revised scale included seven items that were scored on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1, "never", to 5, "always". The BMSS has a Cronbach's alpha of 0.87 showing its internal consistency reliability. c. Motivational Strategies Scale: Adapted from the Patterns of the Adaptive Learning Survey (Midgley et al., 1995). There are four items in the revised scale. The items were scored on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1, "never", to 5, "always". The BMSS has a Cronbach's alpha of 0.77 showing its internal consistency reliability. The present researcher trial-tested the teacher classroom behaviour scales and obtained a Cronbach's alpha 0.85. This is considered adequate.

The Procedure for data collection

The principals of the participating schools were contacted and they gave their approval for the researcher to administer the questionnaires to teachers in their schools. The researcher personally administered the instruments on the respondents with the assistance of four research assistants (postgraduate students in the Faculty of Education, University of Ibadan). The instruments were distributed to the participating teachers in their various schools and were collected after two days' interval. Although one hundred and forty-six (146) questionnaires were administered to the respondents, only one hundred and thirty-two (132) questionnaires were returned. The researcher made use of these 132 (90.4%) of the distributed questionnaires for the computation.

Data analysis

To provide answers to the research questions raised, the data collected was numerically coded and imported into the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25 software. Thereafter, the descriptive statistics of frequency counts, mean and standard deviation were computed while inferential statistics of Pearson moment product correlation (PPMC) and the Multiple regression analysis were used to analyse the data at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research question one: What is the pattern of the relationship between teacher-related factors (teacher self-efficacy, years of teaching experience, and level of teachers' school) and classroom behaviours among teachers in Ibadan Metropolis? The result of this research question is presented on table 1.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics and inter-correlation matrix among the variables

Variable	Mean	SD	1	2	3
1- Classroom behaviour	73.20	10.30	--		
2- Teacher self-efficacy	46.67	9.40	0.363* (0.000)	--	
3- Years of teaching experience	13.87	5.85	0.235* (0.007)	0.124 (0.157)	--
4- Level of teachers' school	2.20	0.75	0.098 (0.264)	0.208* (0.017)	0.017 (0.851)

Table 1 shows that there is a significant relationship between teacher self-efficacy ($r=0.363$, $p<0.05$), years of experience ($r=0.235$, $p<0.05$) and teacher classroom behaviour, but there was no significant relationship between level of teachers' school ($r=0.098$, $p>0.05$), and teacher classroom behaviour. Hence, there is a positive relationship between teacher classroom behaviour and teacher self-efficacy and years of experience. This implies that the more teachers are confident, competent and self-efficacious the better their classroom behaviours in terms of behaviour management, usage of instructional strategies, and motivational strategies will be and these will rub on the students for enhanced student outcomes. Likewise, the longer the teaching experience, the better the teacher classroom behaviours.

Research question two: To what extent do teacher-related factors (teacher self-efficacy, years of teaching experience, and level of teachers' school) jointly contribute to the prediction of classroom behaviours among teachers in Ibadan Metropolis?

Table 2. The Joint contribution of the independent variables to teacher classroom behaviour

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	The Std. Error of the Estimate			
0.411	0.169	0.150	9.494			
A N O V A						
Model	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remark
Regression	2350.084	3	783.361	8.690	0.000	Sig.
Residual	11538.181	128	90.142			
Total	13888.265	131				

Predictors: (Constant), teacher self-efficacy, years of teaching experience, and level of teachers' school; b. Dependent Variable: teacher classroom behaviours

Table 2 shows that the predictive variables (teacher self-efficacy, years of teaching experience, and level of teachers' school) when combined together have significant effects on

teacher classroom behaviours. The table also shows a coefficient of multiple correlation $R = 0.411$ and a multiple R^2 of 0.169. This indicates that when the three predictor variables were combined, they explained 16.9% of the variance.

The significance of the composite contribution was tested at $\alpha = 0.05$. The table also shows that the analysis of variance for the regression yielded F-ratio of 8.690 (significant at 0.05 level). This implies that the joint contribution of the independent variables to the dependent variable was significant and that other variables not included in this model may have accounted for the remaining variance.

Research question three: What is the relative contribution of each of the independent variables (teacher self-efficacy, years of teaching experience and level of teacher's school) to the prediction of the criterion variable (classroom behaviours) among teachers in Ibadan Metropolis?

Table 3. The Relative contribution of the independent variables to the prediction of the teacher classroom behaviour

Model	Unstandardized Coefficient		Stand. Coefficient	t	Sig.	Zero-order	Correlations partial	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta Contribution					Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	50.621	4.742		10.675	0.000				
1	0.366	0.091	0.334	4.029	0.000	0.363	0.335	0.942	1.061
2	0.339	0.143	0.193	2.374	0.019	0.235	0.205	0.985	1.016
3	0.346	1.132	0.025	0.305	0.761	0.098	0.027	0.957	1.045

Key: 1 = Teacher self-efficacy 2 = Years of teaching experience 3 = Level of teachers' school

Table 3 shows that the relative contribution of the independent variables to the dependent variable, expressed as beta weights, is as follows: Teacher self-efficacy ($\beta = 0.334$, $t = 4.029$; $p < 0.05$), years of teaching experience ($\beta = 0.193$, $t = 2.374$; $p < 0.05$), the level of teachers' school ($\beta = 0.025$, $t = 0.305$; $p > 0.05$). This implies that teacher self-efficacy and years of teaching experience could independently and significantly predict teachers' classroom behaviour.

The multicollinearity assumption was assessed with the use of tolerance statistic, and the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) in order to establish the absence of multicollinearity among independent variables. Tolerance values typically range from 0 to 1 with 0.1 serving as a cutoff point (Mertler & Vannatta, 2005). Tolerance values less than 0.1 indicate that there is multicollinearity (a strong relationship between predictor variables). VIF values greater than 10 indicate multicollinearity. Table 3 reveals that while VIF values were less than 10, all tolerance values were greater than 0.1. So, there was no evidence of multicollinearity in this study.

Discussion of findings

Finding of research question one shows that teacher self-efficacy has nexus with classroom behaviour among teachers in Ibadan Metropolis. This finding corroborates that of Suprayogi et al. (2017) that teachers with a high sense of teacher self-efficacy often apply apt differentiated instruction in teaching their students. In the same vein, the present finding is in consonance with

the submission by Tschannen-Moran et al. (2007) that the possibility of classroom behaviour to be improved via high teacher self-efficacy is high. The finding of the present study is also in line with that of Mitchell (2019) that teacher self-efficacy is fundamental to a better classroom environment that is free from aggression and all manners of inappropriate behaviours.

Another finding of this study is in congruence with those of Amadi and Allegoa (2017) that revealed that years of teaching experience has effective contribution to classroom management. The present finding also substantiates that of Nikolaros (2014) that teachers with long teaching experience have the prowess in using suitable instructional strategies that will ensure positive classroom behaviour. The present finding also corroborates those of Lee et al. (2012) that revealed that primary school teachers possess high self-efficacy and instructional conceptual change. Similarly, the present finding supports the finding of Baker (2005) that revealed that primary school teachers were more willing and prepared to implement management strategies for students who are with behavioural deficits.

The second research question shows that the independent variables (three teacher-related factors) jointly contributed 16.9% variance to the prediction of classroom behaviours among teachers. This contribution suggests that other variables not considered in this study could possibly have some contributions to teacher classroom behaviours than the hypothesized variables. This outcome is reasonable, given that some other teacher-related factors not considered in this study could also influence teachers' classroom behaviours.

By implication, when seeking how to improve teacher classroom behaviours, school heads and policy makers in education should address issues that are related to the three factors under investigation in this study that is, teacher self-efficacy, years of teaching experience and level of teachers' school either primary or secondary. In addition, they should endeavour to extend their efforts to understand how other factors such as teacher attitude towards the students, participation in professional training, certifications, teacher-student relationships, teacher mastery of subject taught, class size, use of teaching aids, job satisfaction and remuneration can also affect teacher classroom behaviours. Thereafter, reasonable interventions that are holistic in nature can be implemented. This argument is in line with the finding of Kirondo (2014) that lack of adequate subject mastery by teachers, a large class size and inability to use instructional aids and materials influence teacher use of motivational strategies in a negative way.

The result of the present study as shown in research question three revealed that out of the three predictor variables examined, teacher self-efficacy was the most potent predictor of teacher classroom behaviours. This outcome is expected because it is well reported that teacher self-efficacy has a significant influence on the classroom behaviour of teachers with respect to behaviour management (Egeberg et al., 2021), instructional strategies (Holzberger et al., 2013), and motivational strategies (Kirondo, 2014). Also, Holzberger et al. (2013) indicated that the higher the self-efficacy of teachers, the higher the quality of classroom instruction. Kirondo (2014) reported that when teachers provide motivation to students in the classrooms it leads to efficient learning. This is mainly because teachers' use of motivational strategies in their classrooms has a solid positive influence in motivating students to learn (Guilloteaux & Dörnyei, 2008; Dörnyei & Kubanyiova, 2014; Henry et al., 2018).

Notably, the finding of research question three also demonstrated the potency the influence of years of teaching experience on teacher classroom behaviours. Perhaps, the reason is that long years of teaching experience has the tendency of enabling teachers to gain understanding about different behavioural maladjustments exhibited by diverse students. These teachers are also likely to have understood how to manage the behavioural deficits of their students over the years.

The Implications for teaching reading skills to students with learning disabilities

The findings of this study have implications for teaching reading skills to students with learning disabilities. It is revealed that self-efficacy is a potent tool to achieve optimal results in the teaching of reading skills to students with learning disabilities. This is because teacher self-efficacy would be a useful virtue that can improve teachers' overall performance at work. It would be necessary for the teacher to understand the nature of learning disabilities and the unique characteristics and difficulties that students with learning disabilities face. Teachers would need to recognize that access to the regular education curriculum can be challenging to students with learning disabilities. Teachers would be expected to provide a lot of accommodations, modifications, and also engage in differentiated instruction in addition to teaching content to the students. All these require high teaching self-efficacy. A teacher who does not have high teaching self-efficacy may struggle to perform his duties well and with passion.

As indicated by researchers, since the majority of students with learning disabilities struggle with reading skills, these students would require intensive, individualized, persistent and focused instruction in reading to be able to master other school subjects. Reading is a criterion for success in both curricula and extra-curricular areas. Students with learning disabilities need instruction in basic reading skills such as phonological awareness, fluency, vocabulary development, and reading comprehension (Lazarus, 2009; Khalaf & Santi, 2016). Teaching these skills would require both competence and professional skills like teaching self-efficacy and long years of teaching experience. Teachers, who have high teaching self-efficacy, prepare their reading lessons adequately before going to the class. Such preparations will include choosing the right instructional materials that will drive home their lessons in a very stress free manner and adopting appropriate behaviour management strategies to use in the reading classroom.

The findings of this study have implications for teacher effectiveness, especially with respect to the teaching of reading strategies to students with learning disabilities. After careful consideration of the reading skill to be taught, teachers can choose from a variety of reading instructional strategies such as phonics instruction (Haager & Vaughn, 2013), instructional groupings and peer-mediated reading practices (Boardman et al., 2016, Haager & Vaughn, 2013; Wanzek et al., 2010); collaborative strategic reading (Lazarus, 2009, Boardman et al., 2016). Other reading strategies include repeated reading, partner reading, rhyming, syllable, phoneme awareness activities, daily explicit vocabulary instruction and the use of context clue tasks (Khalaf & Santi, 2016). A teacher's level of self-efficacy is an important determinant of the reading instructional strategy to be selected. Teachers with high self-efficacy know how to select the right reading, instructional strategies for teaching specific contents. In all, it is believed that

teachers who have high teaching self-efficacy would work towards improving their classroom environment, building the self-efficacy and motivation of their students, utilizing suitable teaching strategies in their reading lessons and persevere with their students who experience difficulties in reading until they achieve high student outcomes.

Conclusion

This study investigated the influence of teacher-related factors (teacher self-efficacy, the year of teaching experience and level of teachers' school which could be primary level or secondary level) on classroom behaviours (behaviour management, instructional strategies and motivational strategies) of teachers in Ibadan Metropolis, Oyo State, Nigeria. The findings of the study effectively demonstrated that teacher self-efficacy and the year of teaching experience were positively related to teacher classroom behaviours. It also found that the teacher-related factors (teacher self-efficacy, year of teaching experience and level of teachers' school) when combined together contributed to the prediction of teacher classroom behaviours. The findings also established that teacher self-efficacy was most potent in predicting classroom behaviours among teachers in Ibadan Metropolis.

Recommendations

Teachers especially those who teach reading to students with learning disabilities should make efforts to improve on their self-efficacy. This is because high teacher self-efficacy is related to positive teacher classroom behaviours such as creating a classroom environment that is conducive, encouraging class discussions and meeting the learning requirements of all learners.

Training programmes that focus on building teacher self-efficacy should be held on a regular basis and school heads should ensure that teachers of students with learning disabilities participate in such professional development programmes. By so doing, these teachers will learn how to help the students to succeed and how to develop a resilient spirit necessary for teaching struggling readers and learners. Adequate teacher self-efficacy is also required for teachers to develop challenging learning activities for students with learning disabilities in reading.

Teachers are encouraged to avoid interactions or relationships that could cripple or weaken their self-efficacy and overall teaching competence. Particularly, with respect to teaching reading to students with learning disabilities, some staff may sound discouraging through their attitudes and actions. The highly efficacious teacher should remain focused and on track and decide never to be discouraged on the job. This is important because with the rapid increase in the number of inclusive education practices globally, both regular and special education teachers will be saddled with the tasks of teaching diverse learners in their classrooms.

Certain student behaviours can build or reduce teacher self-efficacy, depending on how it is displayed. Some students with learning disabilities could demonstrate a lack of motivation and this can distract a teacher if he pays attention to such behaviours in the classroom. Rather than get discouraged by students' lack of motivation teachers should boost the motivation of the students and remain focused while teaching these students.

Without appropriate supervision and control in the classroom, there will be no productive teaching and learning. Therefore, irrespective of the years of teaching experience a teacher has acquired or the level of a teacher's school (primary or secondary) he must endeavour to adopt behaviour management strategies that are appropriate to the situation in a given classroom. Teachers must not be lazy, feel uninterested or practice a *lasaiz faire* behaviour in the classroom. They must be ready to direct all activities in the classroom for maximum student outcomes.

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Conflict of Interests

The author declares that there are no conflicts of interests in this study.

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